

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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METHODS OF TREATMENT OF GENITAL INFLAMMATORY DISEASES USING FOLK MEDICINE

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Abstract: This article discusses the treatment of inflammatory diseases of the female genital organs using folk medicine and natural methods.

Key words: folk medicine, genital diseases, namatak, chamomile, honey sedana.

It is known that humanity cannot imagine a society without representatives of refined taste. As the main task of a woman in life is to procreate, unfortunately, we observe that female genitals suffer from certain diseases on regular basis. Inflammatory diseases of genital organs are observed especially in our women. Any discomfort in the human body, especially pain, affects the human nervous system very strongly, and in women, such conditions lead to severe stress, depression, indifference to life and living, and loss self-confidence. And elimination of such situations is sometimes a bit complicated. There are several ways to treat inflammatory diseases of the genitals. Today, they include the use of folk medicine as well as treatment with various chemical drugs. The advantage of folk medicine is that it does not have side effects.

Let`s first have a brief information about what is venereal disease and its symptoms. The following symptoms of genital diseases lead to infertility in women:

- Discharges of various nature from the genitals;
- A rash on the skin and or mucous membrane of the labia major;
- Vagina land;
- Sticky, bloody discharge;
- Pain in the middle of lower abdomen;
- The feeling of the presence of a foreign body in the vagina.

Inflammatory diseases of the genitals can range from mild to unbearable discomfort. Symptoms can be constant or periodic, associated with menstruation or ovulation. In any case, a doctor`s advice is necessary.

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It is observed with symptoms such as pain in the lower abdomen, increased body temperature, restlessness, nausea. Because of this, women`s labor activity slows down. Interest in life weakens.

The use of the following methods of folk medicine in the prevention and treatment of this disease is effective. It is recommended to drink 0.5 cups of raw potato juice every morning for a month. It is effectively used in the treatment of ovarian inflammation.

In addition, it is recommended to drink chamomile tincture and take a bath. To prepare it, a teaspoon of dried chamomile is steeped in half a liter of boiled water for 4 hours. The duration of the practice is one week. And it can be used with chemical drugs. It is especially effective for vaginitis.

Also, taking a tablespoon of dried leaves of the zubturum plant, leaves of the wormwood plant, and the fruit of the namatak plant, steeped like a tea in a liter of water for two hours and consumed four times a day is very useful for inflammatory diseases of the genitals.

In addition, the importance of clove tincture in the treatment of inflammation of the external and internal uterine tubes is very great. It is recommended to take one tablespoon and drink it four to five times a day for a month. It is recommended to drink a liter of water.

Birch leaf, lub herb, licorice rhizome, juniper leaf – taken and mixed in equal amounts. Put 10 grams of it in half a liter of boiled water, heat it in a water bath for 10 minutes, let it rest for two hours in a thermos, and strain it. It is drunk little by little, half a glass three times a day, one hour before meals. Monkey fruit, parsley root, celery root, dastarbosh herb – mix in equal amounts and taste. Put 10 grams of the mixture into boiled water and boil for five minutes. Then it rests in the heat for two hours and drains. Drink half a glass four times a day warm after meals.

Cornflower, grushanka herb, nettle herbs are taken in equal amount and put 8 grams in half a liter of boiled water. It rests in a thermos for four hours and drains. One glass is drunk three to four times a day 30 minutes before meals.

In addition, honey is considered to be a cure for a thousand and one ailments, and it is very useful for diseases of the female genital organs. Consuming honey with black sedana and dabbing the honey on the vagina is a very affective tried and tested method. Additional benefits of honey include tightening the vagina and treating fungal infections.

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In some cases, swelling can be also be observed in inflammatory diseases. In such cases, the benefits of a bath prepared using a decoction of yellow clover and flax seeds are very great. It should be noted that this bath is effective not only for inflammation of the female genital organs, but also for preventing problems in the urinary tract. Because the fact that their location is close to each other also causes the disease to alternate.

Disease prevention is important. It is permissible to pay special attention to the hygiene of intimate areas. It is recommended to wear underwear made of natural fabric, use daily pads only when necessary, change them every three to four hours if there is a lot of discharge, use pads instead of tampons during menstruation.

Avoid wearing any uncomfortable or tight underwear or pants. They can cause increased itching. It is recommended to wash the external genitalia two or three times a day. Chamomile tincture can be used for this purpose, ordinary soap is not suitable.

Anatomical-physiological features of the female body, as well as to protect and prevent them from diseases of the genital organs and venereal diseases, require special cleanliness. From infancy, the external genitalia should be washed every morning and evening with warm (boiling) water or a semi-pink solution of potassium permanganate. Before washing the genitals, wash hands with soap and water.

Since a girl does not have sex hormones in infancy and childhood, her genitals have special anatomical and physiological characteristics. The epithelium of the vagina consists of 2-3 layers of cells (40-50 layers in an adult woman), there are no special microorganisms in the vagina – vaginal bacilli. Because of this, various inflammatory diseases easily occur in this organ. Measles, scarlet fever and other common diseases can cause infection in the vagina.

There are even cases of worms exiting the rectum and entering the vagina. In this case, the skin and mucous membranes are scratched due to the girl's itching, infection and inflammatory diseases occur

In short, folk medicine is used in combination with chemical methods for benign genital inflammatory diseases.

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